

A Life of Isolation and Introspection in the Select Novels of Anita Desai, Kiran Desai and Jhumpa Lahiri

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: February

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2321-788X

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:

Tamil Selvi, P. "A Life of Isolation and Introspection in the Select Novels of Anita Desai, Kiran Desai and Jhumpa Lahiri." *Shanlax International Journal of Arts, Science and Humanities*, vol. 6, no. S1, 2019, pp. 33–35.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2556583>

Mrs.P.Tamil Selvi

*Former Assistant Professor, Department of English
E.M.G.Yadava College, Madurai*

Abstract

The Indian women writers in English literature are taken essential part to describe the society. Writers like Anita Desai, Kiran Desai and Jhumpa Lahiri portrayed the feelings of isolation, sense of detachment, mental fatigue, and longing for motherland. They explained about these multiple senses and experiences by the human beings. And also their writings contain the family problems, misunderstanding with one another, rejection by husband, isolation, and depression and so on.

Introduction

In the world women play an important role in every one's life. From the beginning women contribute something special to the world. She plays multiple role during her life time as a daughter, sister, wife, mother and grandmother. When she comes to the world by birth she bears more problems and tolerates other's disturbances. When she is married she has to adapt and adjust her husband family. And urged to render service there. All her life she depends her husband. Sometimes such a dependency gives boredom to her. She understands that there is a freedom activity beyond the family and also the society needs her contribution. So she thinks and realizes her power. Gradually she thinks about the society and her position. She starts to write. She reveals her thoughts through poem, story, novel, and so on. She observes her family members and the neighborhood people and their problems and sufferings and also how the women are facing problems on their own without making any noise.

A Life of Isolation and Introspection

Anita Desai is specially noted for her insightful depiction of the inner life of the female characters in her writings. In many of her works she has highlighted the tensions among the family members and estrangement of middle – class women. She wrote her first novel in the year 1963 "Cry, the Peacock". It was followed by "Fire on the Mountain", "Bye Bye Blackbird". "Where shall we go this Summer?" and other significant works. Her works were short listed for the Booker prize three times.

Anita Desai explained that all her writing is "... an effort to discover, to underline and convey the true significance of things. That is why, in my novels, small objects, passing moods and attitudes acquire a large importance... one hope, at the end of one's career, to have made some significant statement on life – not set of rules, shifting and kinetic one that remains always capable of further change and growth".

Anita Desai's "Cry, the peacock" is a novel deals with the feelings of isolation to the woman who feels loneliness and rejected by husband. The Novel is told in the form of a first-person narrative and in retrospect. The past memories of Maya, which form the bulk of the Novel, and she has done her husband Gautama to death. In fact, she had never been sane during her 4 years of married life. She blames Gautama's coldness on his incessant talk of cups of tea and philosophy with which he shielded himself against the cries of her heart. She suffered his neglect and sulked before becoming quite. They were locked in a deadly love-hate relationship. Gautama's dry intellectualism that forces the ideal of detachment down her unwilling throat and wants her to dismiss sorrow as an illusion

Anita Desai's "Fire on the mountain" is the elegant Novel about Nanda Kaul who is an old widow. Nanda, tired of playing the role of wife, retires to a secluded place. It is sheer weariness, mental fatigue that prompts her to move away from the world of duty and responsibility. She is the wife of Mr.Kaul; vice – chancellor of Punjab University. She retires in her old age to the hill station resort to Kasauli. Carignano is a villa away from the maddening crowd, looking across to the snows of the distant Himalayas, down to the hot, dusty plains below. She lives here all by herself, and maintains a stoic posture of proud indifference to the rest of the world. She leads a life of isolation and introspection. She does not even like the arrival of the postman for delivering letters. But her great grand daughter Raka interrupts her summer peace. She hates Raka, for disturbing her solitary life. Both live a separate life inside one home.

Solitude and Crush of Life

As might be expected from the rich input of her cultural background, Kiran Desai, daughter of Anita Desai, is a born story – teller. Desai is the youngest woman to win the coveted Booker Prize for her second novel, *The Inheritance of Loss* (2006). She spent eight years for writing this second novel. In this novel Desai portrays the issue of poverty and globalization not being an easy solution for the problems of trapped social middle classes.

Kiran Desai's second Novel "The Inheritance of Loss" is set partly in India and partly in the US. The retired Judge Jemubhai Patel in England in his boyhood grew lonely and came to love his solitude. The solitude became a habit, the habit became the man, and it crushed him into a shadow. The novel follows the journey of Biju, an illegal immigrant in US who is trying to make a new life; and Sai, an Anglicised Indian girl living with her grandfather Jemubhai Patel in India.

Biju keeps moving from one job to another in the several basement kitchens in New York with different nationalities- all illegal immigrants- working there. He continually worries about being picked up by immigration and longs to be back in his village. He is angry with his father for sending him alone to this country. One day he slips on rotten spinach in the kitchen and hurts his leg. His employer refuses him any medical help because it is expensive and also he is an illegal immigrant. Instead his employer asks Biju to go back to India, get treated, and return to America. But how can Biju do it without a green card. He gets isolated with pain. After a long struggle and tedious flight, he arrives in Calcutta and smells

India again. Biju steps out of the airport in Calcutta and feels like a baby on his mother's lap. On his way to Kalimpong from Siliguri, Biju is stripped and robbed by the revolutionaries. As he sits alone in the forest at night and he has lost even his dignity and pride.

Isolation Makes Longing for Motherland

Pulitzer Prize winner Jhumpa Lahiri's novel "The Namesake" explains about the life of Ashima Ganguli and her husband Ashoke Ganguli in America. She gets delivery pain as carries a child, two weeks before her due date. She is admitted in Mount Auburn Hospital. She is alone in hospital because of its rules, cut off by curtains from the three other women in the room. It is the first time in her life, she has slept alone, surrounded by strangers; all her life she has slept either in a room with her parents, or with Ashoke at her side. Ashima thinks it's strange that her child will be born in a place most people enter either to suffer or to die. There is nothing to comfort her. She thinks if it is in India women go home to their parents to give birth, away from husbands and in-laws and household cares, retreating briefly to childhood when the baby arrives. In hospital Dr. Ashley pokes in his head from time to time. "No need to worry", he chirps, putting a stethoscope to her belly, patting Ashima's hand, admiring her various bracelets. "Everything is looking perfectly normal. We are expecting a perfectly normal delivery, Mrs. Ganguli". But nothing feels normal to Ashima. For the past eighteen months, ever since this arrived in Cambridge, nothing has felt normal at all. It's not so much the pain, which she knows, somehow, she will survive. It's the consequence motherhood in a foreign land. For it was one thing to be pregnant, to suffer the queasy mornings in bed, the sleepless nights, the dull throbbing in her back, the countless visits to the bathroom. Throughout the experience, in spite of her growing discomfort, she'd been astonished by her body's ability to make life exactly as her mother and grandmother and all her great grandmothers had done. That it was happening so far from home, unmonitored and unobserved by those she loved, had made it more miraculous still. And also she is terrified to raise a child in a country where she is related to no one, where she knows so little, where life seems so tentative and spare. Without a single grandparent or parent or uncle or aunt at her side, the baby's birth, like most everything else in America, feels somehow haphazard. She said to Ashoka, "I don't want to raise Gogol alone in this country. It's not right. I want to go back".

Conclusion

Thus Anita Desai, Kiran Desai, and Jhumpa Lahiri revealed their intuition through their writings. They swam against the immigrant problems and faced the social imbalances. The theme of isolation in the world of literature witnessed by the Indian writers who are settled abroad. In such a way these great women writers proved their skills through their writings.

References

- Batra, Shakthi. "Fire on the Mountain - A Critical Study". Delhi, *Surject Publications*, 2018.
- Batra, Shakthi. "The Inheritance of Loss - Critical Study". Delhi, *Surject Publications*, 2017.
- Desai, Anita. "Cry the Peacock", New Delhi Divisions, Orient Paper backs, 1980.
- Lahiri, "Jhumpa The Namesake, London Flamingo An Imprint of Harper". Collins Publishers, 2003.
- Desai, Anita, "Replies to the Questionnaire", *Kakatiys Journal of English Studies*, vol. 3, 1990.